

RESULTS AND BENEFITS OF ULTRASOUND EXAMINATION IN ACUTE SCROTAL SYNDROME

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Relevance: The problem of acute scrotum (AS) in children is one of the most pressing problems in pediatric surgery, accounting for about 20% of all emergency pathologies in childhood [3, 4, 8, 10]. Among acute testicular diseases in children, the first place in terms of prevalence is pathology of the testicles and epididymis (torsion and necrosis of the hydatid). The next place is occupied by testicular torsion, nonspecific orchiepididymitis [1, 2, 7, 8], and traumatic injuries. Most of the above conditions require prompt diagnosis [5, 6, 9]. In conclusion, it is necessary to develop general and non-invasive criteria, such as ultrasound, when diagnosing AS in such cases.

Purpose of the study. Optimization of non-invasive diagnostic methods for acute inflammation of the scrotum in children.

Material and research methods. The results of treatment of children aged 1 to 18 years with acute scrotal syndrome were studied. Of these, 124 (61.4%) patients had torsion of the testicular hydatid, 57 (28.2%) had testicular torsion, and 21 (10.0%) had inflammation of the testicle and its elements. The results of ultrasound examination of patients with acute scrotal syndrome were used.

Results of the study. In 41% of patients with uncomplicated hydatid torsion, minimal changes in the organs of the scrotum were detected by ultrasound; in 56.1% of patients with testicular torsion, there was a violation of the adjacent skin of the testicular vagina, in the structures of the spermatic cord of its part of the scrotum.

Conclusion. With testicular torsion, the ultrasound criterion is an increase in blood flow in the internal organs by 2-4 times, an increase in the size of the testicle, heterogeneity of composition, and with hydatid torsion, the blood flow increases to 10% of normal. significant (>20%) enlargement of the testicle. An average enlargement of the testicle with a moderate increase in blood flow (up to 10%) is regarded as acute epididymitis, and an increase in testicular size with an increase in blood flow up to 10% of the norm is considered an ultrasound criterion for acute orchitis.

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